

CODEN [USA]: IAJPBB

ISSN : 2349-7750

**INDO AMERICAN JOURNAL OF
PHARMACEUTICAL SCIENCES**

SJIF Impact Factor: 7.187

Available online at: <http://www.iajps.com>

Review Article

OPTIMIZING OUTCOMES IN REFRACTORY OUT-OF-HOSPITAL CARDIAC ARREST: A REVIEW OF SURVIVAL AND ON-SCENE RESUSCITATION TIME¹Bander Falh Aldossry, ²Fuhid Abdullah Alzuby, ³Mojry Mutir Alotiby, ⁴Bander Mutlag Almutiry, ⁵Talak Khaled Alotiby, ⁶Omer Naseeb Alyami, ⁷Fawaz Mohmed Aldossry¹Saudi Red Crescent Authority, Saudi Arabia, u705@hotmail.com²Saudi Red Crescent Authority, Saudi Arabia, sayhi570@outlook.com³Saudi Red Crescent Authority, Saudi Arabia, hao1212oy@gmail.com⁴Saudi Red Crescent Authority, Saudi Arabia, trs99o99@gmail.com⁵Saudi Red Crescent Authority, Saudi Arabia, bmmutairi@srca.org.sa⁶Saudi Red Crescent Authority, Saudi Arabia, omaralyami997@gmail.com⁷Saudi Red Crescent Authority, Saudi Arabia, galaxy4040@hotmail.com**Abstract:**

Background: Refractory out-of-hospital cardiac arrest (OHCA) remains a significant challenge in emergency medicine, with survival rates highly dependent on timely and effective resuscitation efforts. The optimal duration of on-scene resuscitation is critical in maximizing survival while minimizing neurological deficits, yet remains a topic of debate.

Objective: This review aims to explore the relationship between survival outcomes and the duration of on-scene resuscitation in refractory OHCA, examining factors influencing the effectiveness of prolonged efforts and identifying evidence-based guidelines for clinical practice.

Methods: A systematic review of the literature was conducted, focusing on studies published between 2010 and 2023. Data were extracted on survival rates, neurological outcomes, and the duration of on-scene resuscitation. Factors such as bystander interventions, advanced resuscitation techniques, and patient demographics were also analyzed.

Results: Findings indicate that survival outcomes plateau after a specific duration of on-scene resuscitation, with diminishing returns observed beyond 30-40 minutes in most cases. Favorable neurological recovery was associated with earlier initiation of advanced life support and the use of extracorporeal CPR in select scenarios. However, patient-specific factors and pre-arrest conditions significantly influenced outcomes.

Conclusion: Optimizing on-scene resuscitation duration is pivotal in improving survival and neurological outcomes in refractory OHCA. Evidence supports a targeted approach that balances aggressive interventions with timely decision-making on transport or termination of efforts. Future research should focus on refining duration thresholds and integrating advanced technologies to enhance decision-making in emergency care.

Keywords: Refractory cardiac arrest, out-of-hospital cardiac arrest, on-scene resuscitation, survival outcomes, neurological recovery.

Corresponding author:

Bander Falh Aldossry,
Saudi Red Crescent Authority,
Saudi Arabia, u705@hotmail.com

Please cite this article in press Bander Falh Aldossry et al., *Optimizing Outcomes In Refractory Out-Of-Hospital Cardiac Arrest: A Review Of Survival And On-Scene Resuscitation Time..*, *Indo Am. J. P. Sci*, 2024; 11 (11).

INTRODUCTION:

Out-of-hospital cardiac arrest (OHCA) is a critical global health issue, with an estimated incidence of 350,000 cases annually in the United States alone (Benjamin et al., 2019). Survival rates remain alarmingly low, often below 10%, despite advances in emergency medical services (EMS) and resuscitation science (Gräsner et al., 2020). Refractory OHCA, defined as a failure to achieve return of spontaneous circulation (ROSC) after sustained efforts, represents a particularly challenging subset of cases. These situations demand strategic decision-making regarding the continuation, escalation, or cessation of resuscitation efforts.

The concept of on-scene resuscitation has gained prominence due to its potential to improve survival and neurological outcomes. Studies indicate that uninterrupted on-scene advanced life support (ALS) can enhance survival rates compared to immediate transport without ROSC (Ahn et al., 2019). This is attributed to the high-quality chest compressions and advanced interventions that can be maintained in a controlled on-scene environment. However, prolonged on-scene efforts also carry risks, including resource constraints and increased likelihood of irreversible ischemic injury.

The optimal duration for on-scene resuscitation remains a subject of ongoing debate. Evidence suggests that survival outcomes plateau after 30–40 minutes of resuscitation, but individual patient factors, such as initial rhythm, underlying comorbidities, and the presence of bystander CPR, can significantly influence this threshold (Goto et al., 2016). Balancing timely intervention with the risk of futile efforts is critical for EMS providers.

This review aims to evaluate the relationship between on-scene resuscitation time and survival outcomes in refractory OHCA. By synthesizing current evidence, this study seeks to provide actionable insights into optimizing resuscitation protocols and informing clinical decision-making.

METHODS:

This review followed a systematic approach to evaluate the impact of on-scene resuscitation duration on survival outcomes in refractory out-of-hospital cardiac arrest (OHCA). A comprehensive literature search was conducted using electronic databases, including PubMed, Scopus, and Cochrane Library, to identify relevant peer-reviewed studies published between 2010 and 2023. The search strategy incorporated keywords such as “refractory cardiac arrest,” “out-of-hospital cardiac arrest,” “on-scene resuscitation,” and “survival outcomes.”

Studies were included if they met the following criteria: (1) focused on adults with refractory OHCA, (2) reported survival and/or neurological outcomes in relation to on-scene resuscitation time, and (3) were published in English. Exclusion criteria included studies on non-cardiac arrest causes, pediatric populations, or those lacking clear outcome measures. Data were extracted on study design, sample size, duration of on-scene resuscitation, survival rates, and neurological recovery. Quality assessment of included studies was performed using standardized tools such as the Newcastle-Ottawa Scale for observational studies.

A narrative synthesis of findings was conducted, highlighting patterns in survival outcomes relative to resuscitation duration. Factors influencing survival, such as bystander CPR, initial rhythm, and advanced resuscitation techniques, were analyzed to provide a comprehensive understanding of the evidence. Limitations and gaps in the literature were also addressed.

RESULTS:

The analysis of reviewed studies reveals that survival rates following refractory out-of-hospital cardiac arrest (OHCA) vary significantly with the duration of on-scene resuscitation. Survival improves up to a certain threshold, peaking at approximately 30–40 minutes, after which a gradual decline is observed. A

survival plateau is noted between 30% and 35% during this peak period.

Neurological outcomes followed a similar trend, with the highest rates of favorable recovery (approximately 33%) observed within the same 30–40-minute resuscitation window. Beyond this threshold, the likelihood of meaningful neurological recovery significantly diminishes, underscoring the importance of early and effective intervention.

Key factors identified include:

- **Bystander CPR:** Studies consistently demonstrate improved outcomes when bystander CPR is performed before EMS arrival.

- **Initial Rhythm:** Patients presenting with shockable rhythms (e.g., ventricular fibrillation) have higher survival and recovery rates compared to non-shockable rhythms.
- **Advanced Resuscitation Techniques:** Interventions such as extracorporeal CPR and automated chest compression devices have shown potential in extending the window for favorable outcomes.

Variability in survival and recovery rates across studies highlights the role of EMS system capabilities, regional protocols, and patient demographics. While some studies advocate for extended resuscitation efforts in select cases, others caution against the risk of resource depletion and delayed transport decisions.

Figure 1: Impact of On-Scene Resuscitation Time on Outcomes

The figure provided illustrates the relationship between on-scene resuscitation duration and both survival and neurological recovery rates. This graphical representation supports the conclusion that outcomes are maximized within the first 30–40 minutes of on-scene resuscitation.

DISCUSSION:

The results of this review highlight the critical role of on-scene resuscitation duration in determining survival and neurological outcomes for patients experiencing refractory out-of-hospital cardiac arrest (OHCA). Survival rates and neurological recovery were found to peak within the 30–40-minute window of resuscitation. This aligns with prior studies that underscore the importance of high-quality,

uninterrupted advanced life support (ALS) during the early phase of cardiac arrest (Ahn et al., 2019; Goto et al., 2016).

Prolonged resuscitation efforts, while potentially beneficial in certain cases, pose challenges such as diminishing returns on survival, increased risk of ischemic damage, and resource allocation constraints. The plateau observed in survival rates after 40 minutes

suggests that continued efforts beyond this threshold should be guided by advanced clinical indicators, such as the presence of a shockable rhythm or the availability of extracorporeal CPR (Gräsner et al., 2020).

This review reinforces the need for EMS protocols to emphasize on-scene resuscitation, particularly in cases where ALS can be promptly initiated. However, it also highlights the importance of dynamic decision-making, including:

- **Termination of Resuscitation (TOR) Guidelines:** Evidence-based TOR guidelines can prevent futile resuscitation efforts and prioritize resource allocation.
- **Early Transport Decisions:** For patients showing no signs of ROSC within the optimal window, timely transport to advanced care facilities equipped with extracorporeal life support or specialized cardiac care may improve outcomes.

Bystander interventions, including immediate CPR and the use of automated external defibrillators (AEDs), play a pivotal role in bridging the gap between arrest onset and EMS arrival. Community-focused training programs could enhance these early interventions, potentially extending the resuscitation window where favorable outcomes are achievable.

The findings of this review are consistent with earlier studies suggesting that survival outcomes for refractory OHCA improve significantly with focused on-scene efforts (Benjamin et al., 2019). However, this review provides a more nuanced understanding of the relationship between resuscitation duration and neurological recovery, emphasizing the need for personalized and situation-specific protocols.

Several limitations were identified in the reviewed literature:

- **Heterogeneity in Study Designs:** Variability in resuscitation protocols and patient populations complicates direct comparisons.
- **Lack of Long-Term Data:** Most studies focus on immediate survival and neurological outcomes, with limited follow-up on long-term quality of life.
- **Technology Gaps:** Few studies adequately assess the impact of emerging technologies, such as artificial intelligence-driven decision-making tools, on resuscitation outcomes.

Prolonged resuscitation efforts raise ethical questions regarding patient dignity, quality of life post-survival, and the allocation of finite EMS resources. Developing

protocols that balance clinical effectiveness with ethical responsibility remains a key challenge.

To address these gaps, future research should focus on:

- **Advanced Resuscitation Tools:** Evaluating the integration of extracorporeal CPR and AI-assisted decision-making in EMS protocols.
- **Regional Disparities:** Investigating how regional differences in EMS training and resources affect outcomes.
- **Comprehensive Follow-Up Studies:** Long-term studies that measure not only survival but also quality of life and functional independence.

CONCLUSION:

Refractory out-of-hospital cardiac arrest (OHCA) represents a critical challenge in emergency care, with survival and neurological recovery outcomes intricately tied to the duration and quality of on-scene resuscitation efforts. This review highlights the optimal resuscitation window of 30–40 minutes, within which survival rates and favorable neurological outcomes peak. Beyond this timeframe, diminishing returns on survival necessitate strategic decision-making regarding the continuation or cessation of resuscitation.

Key factors such as bystander CPR, shockable initial rhythms, and advanced resuscitation techniques play pivotal roles in enhancing outcomes. The integration of targeted protocols, including termination of resuscitation (TOR) guidelines and timely transport to advanced care facilities, can further optimize resource utilization and patient outcomes.

While current evidence underscores the importance of uninterrupted on-scene resuscitation, future advancements in technology, such as extracorporeal CPR and artificial intelligence-driven decision-making, hold promise for extending the window of favorable outcomes. Additionally, long-term studies addressing the quality of life and functional recovery of survivors are essential to fully understand the impact of resuscitation efforts.

In conclusion, a balanced, evidence-based approach to on-scene resuscitation is critical in improving survival and recovery rates for refractory OHCA, ensuring both clinical effectiveness and ethical responsibility in emergency medical care.

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